

Supplementary materials - DeepSeek reasoning traces under different prompting conditions

This document complements the conference companion "AI and Renaissance Poetry: How Prompt Language Shapes Literary Translation" (Tenace, 2026) by providing the visual evidence underlying the observation, reported in section 6 of the main paper, that variation emerges not only at the output level but also in the generated reasoning traces exposed by the model interface.

What the reader is looking at

DeepSeek R1 is a reasoning-augmented Large Language Model that, alongside its final translation output, exposes a structured trace of the intermediate steps it follows when processing a prompt. This trace, labelled "Ragionamento con R1" in the system interface, lists the analytical stages externalised by the interface- for example, the identification of rhetorical figures, the analysis of the rhyme scheme, the selection of metaphors, and the planning of stylistic choices. The screenshots reproduced in this supplementary, capture the reasoning traces exposed through the interface for both prompting conditions tested in the study.

What to observe

The two reasoning traces share a common backbone, both identify rhetorical figures, recognise the metrical scheme, and conclude with a preservation declaration listing the stylistic elements the model intends to safeguard in translation. The traces differ, however, along four axes. First, in **granularity**: the Italian-prompt trace unfolds across seven analytical steps, the English-prompt trace across twelve, with substantially more detailed line-by-line examination in the latter. Second, in the presence of an **explicit priority hierarchy**: the English-prompt condition concludes with a declared ranking of translation priorities ("Musicality over literalness", "Conceptual fidelity to Petrarchan oxymorons", "Dynamic equivalence of Renaissance poetic conventions"), an element entirely absent from the Italian-prompt trace. Third, in **terminological register**: the English-prompt trace adopts a markedly more critical-literary vocabulary, with explicit reference to fire imagery, Petrarchan oxymorons (see fig.3), and Renaissance poetic conventions, whereas the Italian-prompt trace remains predominantly procedural in its terminology. Fourth, the Italian-prompt condition produces a **partially bilingual trace** predominantly in English but retaining an Italian interface marker whereas the English-prompt condition remains fully monolingual.

This qualitative contrast offers preliminary qualitative indications that prompt language influences not only the surface form of the translation but also the granularity of the model's analysis and its tendency to externalise an explicit stylistic/strategic framework - a finding that, while based on a single sonnet, indicates a direction worth investigating systematically in the extended study.

An additional observation emerged within the English-prompt reasoning process itself. In different stages of the generated chain-of-thought explanation, the model identified two distinct Petrarchan rhyme schemes ("ABBA ABBA CDE DCE" and "ABBA ABBA CDC DCD") within the same translation condition.

While both patterns are compatible with Petrarchan sonnet structures, this internal inconsistency may reflect inconsistency in the generated metrical reasoning or in its explicit reasoning about poetic form. The observation does not necessarily invalidate the generated translation, but it raises interesting questions regarding the coherence and reliability of AI-generated literary reasoning processes.

Configuration

All traces were generated through the DeepSeek R1 model (free-tier web interface), queried on 26th February 2025 under default sampling parameters. Single-run illustrative example, acknowledged as a limitation. The screenshots have not been edited; only the surrounding the platform interface (Chrome) has been cropped for readability.

Italian prompt condition:

Fig. S1 - Chain-of-thought trace produced by DeepSeek R1 under Italian prompt («Traduci questa poesia di Petrarca in inglese»). The trace unfolds across seven analytical steps, illustrating how the model decomposes the task into rhetorical inspection — including the identification of the hypallage in «pietosi color» — structural analysis of quatrains and tercets, and incremental translation, followed by a concluding evaluation of the rendered text.

English prompt condition

Ragionamento con R1

- 1. Translating Petrarch's poem into English while preserving its poetic structure and...
- 2. Okay, so I need to translate Petrarch's sonnet into English. Let me start by reading...
- 3. First, I'll analyze each line of the Italian poem. The first quatrain talks about golden...
- 4. Next line: "e 'l vago lume oltra misura ardea / di quei begli occhi, ch'or ne son sì..."
- 5. Then there's the hypallage in "pietosi color." The example uses "mercy's hues" to...
- 6. The second quatrain deals with the speaker's uncertainty if the colors are true or...
- 7. In the tercets, Petrarch describes her walk as angelic and her words beyond...
- 8. The final lines mention a celestial spirit and a living sun, ending with the metaphor...
- 9. I need to check the rhyme scheme. The original is ABBA ABBA CDE DCE. The...
- 10. Also, maintain the hypallage in line 5. The user's example notes it, so I should...
- 11. Check the meter. Petrarch's sonnets are typically hendecasyllabic. The example...
- 12. Finally, the closing couplet about the unhealed wound. The example uses "bows..."

Gathered sufficient information

Fig. S2 - DeepSeek R1 reasoning trace under English prompt ("Translate this Petrarch poem into English"). The trace unfolds across twelve analytical steps, with explicit attention to literary devices (notably the hypallage in «pietosi color», to the rhyme scheme (ABBA ABBA CDE DCE), to the fire imagery and the archer metaphor of the closing couplet, and to the hendecasyllabic meter. The reasoning is substantially more articulated than under the Italian prompt (Fig. S1).

Key preservation elements:

- **Hypallage** in "pity's hues" (transferred epithet from face to colors)
- **ABBA ABBA CDC DCD** rhyme scheme (adapting Petrarchan form)
- **Fire imagery** ("blaze," "combustion," "Sun") mirroring Italian "ardea"/"arsi"
- **Paradox** of sacred/profane love through "celestial spirit"/"wounds"
- **Archer metaphor** maintained in final couplet ("bow"/"arrows")

This translation prioritizes:

1. Musicality over literalness ("Zephyr's play" vs literal "aura")
2. Conceptual fidelity to Petrarchan oxymorons
3. Dynamic equivalence of Renaissance poetic conventions

Fig. S3 - Stylistic priorities declared by DeepSeek R1 at the end of the English-prompt reasoning trace. The model explicitly states five preservation targets (hypallage, rhyme scheme, fire imagery, sacred/profane paradox, archer metaphor) and three translation priorities (musicality over literalness, conceptual fidelity to Petrarchan oxymorons, dynamic equivalence of Renaissance poetic conventions). Such an explicit stylistic framework does not surface in the Italian-prompt condition.